

Positive and Negative Effects of Psychology on Nutrition, Diet and Eating Habits

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Abstract

Our eating habits are linked to our psychological state. It is seen that people who eat a lot of food are under stress (Güven, 2014). Psychological discomfort or conditions can change people's eating habits. It is seen that people's eating habits are related to the job they work, the country they live in, and the culture they grew up in. In addition, there are many factors that affect our eating habits psychologically. It is observed that people under stress eat more frequently or rarely (Gibson, 2006). Emotional and psychological states change eating habits. An event that happens to us while starting a healthy diet can cause the diet to be disrupted. This situation, called emotional eating, is due to psychological effects. There are situations that cause the person to go out of their usual nutritional state. Stress and sadness can lead a person to consume food. Working conditions in developed countries make people tired psychologically. Due to working hours and the frequency of work, many people work under the pressure of stress. For this reason, it is seen that more obesity disorders occur in developing or fully developed countries today (Güven, 2014). Depression and fatigue are thought to have a direct impact on people's diet. Some people have an excessive appetite, while others have the opposite effect. Psychological traumas cause sudden changes in people's eating habits. Also, when happy, many people tend to eat. To understand what the psychological effect is here, it

is necessary to examine the country, job, age, gender, and all other situations of the individuals. While psychological problems can affect the diet negatively, some psychological conditions can affect the eating habits positively.

Keywords: *Psychology and Nutrition, Effects of Psychology on Eating Habits, Psychology and Diet, Stress and Nutrition*

1. Introduction

In this article, the positive and negative effects of psychology on eating habits are examined in depth. People are social beings. Today, people's eating habits are highly influenced by their environment. Changes in the eating habits of psychologically diagnosed people have been observed. In societies that think that perfection has to do with weakness and fitness, eating habits change accordingly. Obesity and obesity diseases are quite common in developed countries (Gibson, 2006). Considering the working conditions and conditions, psychological factors affecting the eating habit stand out. Stress, sadness, happiness, and psychological fatigue have a direct effect on nutrition and eating habits. Due to the psychological pressures and norms brought by the social environment, many people make changes in their diets and make weight gain programs, diet, and similar practices. These effects cause thoughts that suggest that you will feel better when you are psychologically weakened or gain weight. It is observed that people tend to eat when working conditions are stressful, tiring, or boring (Pengulu et al., 2019). The work or living conditions in which they are psychologically affected have a direct impact on their eating habits. In a study, it was observed that the individual tends to eat more after a psychological trauma (Heuvel et al., 2019). Psychology can have positive and negative effects on nutrition. To classify these effects as positive or negative, psychological conditions need to be deeply examined.

There is a society where beauty is linked to the perception of weakness and different communities that think that being overweight is beauty. Therefore, it is necessary to dig deep into the psychological state to understand whether the effect is positive or negative (Arganini et al., 2012). Psychological states such as emotional eating are linked to stress, sadness, and

other emotional traumas and can cause people to eat more (Macht and Simons, 2011). The negative effects of psychology on nutrition can lead to profoundly serious health problems if left untreated and especially common diseases such as obesity are usually caused by the effects of psychological conditions (Lobera ve Martínez, 2020).

Psychology has many effects on the actions we perform physiologically. Since nutritional patterns are examined, differences are observed between people and communities. Distinctions such as carnivore and herbivore are quite common in the world. While culture affects these concepts, situations such as loss of appetite, desire to overeat, tendency to consume harmful foods or not eating anything can be caused by the effects of psychology. On the day when he is incredibly happy, a person can forget to eat when he returns home and focus on the situation that creates happiness and affects his psychology. But people who experience a distressed psychological state often tend to eat too much. This is called emotional eating in psychology (Lobera and Martínez, 2020). The psychological state of the individual can directly affect his nutrition. It has been observed that individuals working under stress often eat unhealthy foods and may have physiological disorders up to obesity (Macht and Simons, 2011). Stress is one of the key factors to understand the relationship between psychology and eating habits, and because of stress, many individuals face many ailments around the world, such as obesity and loss of appetite. (Rooke and Thorsteinsson, 2008).

2. Stress and Nutrition

People who tend to eat at night are stressed, and this is associated with connections in the hypothalamus-pituitary region of their brains, and stress is effective on diet and even on many issues, including carbohydrate, protein, and fat selection (Takeda et al., 2004). Stress, one of the biggest factors affecting our psychology, directly affects us in every aspect of our lives. When eating habits were examined, it was observed that people who were upset or under stress ate more often and turned to unhealthy foods to overcome or forget about it (Lobera and Martínez, 2020). The effects of psychology on eating habits can be both negative and positive, so to understand the relationship between stress and nutrition and to enable individuals to acquire healthier eating habits, it is necessary to understand the relationship between these two

concepts in detail and to produce solutions. In the research, it is seen that many people turn to less and regular nutrition due to the stress caused by the stress caused by being weaker in their environment triggers the perception of beauty (Gibson, 2006). It has been proven by many case studies that nutrition and stress are linked (Arganini et al., 2012). The psychological state of the individual is linked to the choice of foods in which he feeds. Especially in developed societies, increasing coffee consumption, ready meals and the health problems caused by them can be clearly seen (Sanchez et al., 2022). In cases where the individual is psychologically exposed to stress, it is observed that the eating pattern changes and makes unusual choices (Macht and Simons, 2011).

Nutritional disorders caused by psychological stress can be seen. Today, the reactions of people who are psychologically stressed to this situation through their nutrition may vary (Heuvel et al., 2019). While some people try to improve their psychological state through nutrition by turning to emotional nutrition, others show a lack of appetite by cutting themselves off from eating and the opposite effect occurs. Moreover, individuals can change their eating habits due to psychological effects depending on many varied factors such as culture, environment, and country they are in and can adjust them accordingly. There are many cases in the US study that say that coffee consumption is used to relieve stress (Luszczynska et al., 2004). Moreover, there are different cases of people changing their diet to cope with stress management and saying that they overcome it by eating different foods (Arganini et al., 2012).

The effects of psychology on eating habits may differ in a way that affects the outcome of the situation that arises (Takeda et al., 2004). While the reactions of individuals when under stress may vary, at the same time the changes they will make in their eating habits may change. For this reason, when examining the changes in nutritional habits that the individual will experience due to psychological stress, many factors such as culture, work, age, gender, race, country, and economic situation should be taken into consideration. With the simplest example, due to the negative perception of beauty in society against people with obesity, it can be observed that these individuals change their nutrition with healthier and weight loss patterns under this stress (Şengönül et al., 2019). While changing the eating habits of the situations that

affect individuals psychologically, it is seen that this change is not the same and differs between individuals. Depending on the cause and duration of stress, nutrition may change and result in loss of appetite (Hawks et al., 2003). While the consequences of eating habits can cause stress on their own, stress is also highly effective on eating habits. Sudden drops in blood sugar due to stress in situations described as dessert crises can be given as an example of this situation (Macht and Simons, 2000).

The underlying factors of psychological stress vary. For this reason, when examining nutritional habits, it is necessary to pay attention to the reason that pushes the individual to this change. While the cause of stress in societies where a weak person is considered beautiful is the perception of beauty, excessive food consumption due to stress can be shown as an example of the effect of stress on nutrition (Özenoğlu, 2017). It is known that the effects of unhealthy nutrition are the basis of depressive mood disorders. When the body does not receive enough minerals, vitamins and foods, our body can negatively affect our psychology and cause us to turn to trends that result in psychological stress, and the foods that affect our psychology, which we call functional food, have become increasingly common in the last fifty years (Özcan, 2018). It has been observed that people who aim to get away from the negative emotions and psychological stress they are found by eating turn to emotional nutrition and consume more delicious, caloric, or favorite foods (Seven, 2013). The stress hormone is also known to psychologically cause feelings of hunger in people.

Individuals may react differently when faced with psychological stress. When such reasons are examined, it is seen that stress and nutrition are linked and at the same time affect individuals psychologically and physiologically. As it is known that depressed individuals often suffer from obesity by eating, it is seen that people who suffer from obesity experience psychological stress due to the existing situation and therefore become depressed (Rooke and Thorsteinsson, 2008). Due to psychological stress, behaviors such as excessive loss of appetite, very low-calorie diet and death diet may be encountered in some individuals as a reverse, and therefore the effect of psychological stress on eating habits needs to be examined in depth (Takeda et al., 2004).

3. The Positive Effects of Psychology on Nutrition

The situations we experience emotionally affect our eating habits, speed, and even digestion time. Therefore, when our psychology is positive, the body will go to an easier digestion (Macht and Simons, 2000). It is also necessary to examine the concept called self-esteem here. For the self-esteem of the individual to be high, lies the perception of weakness that falls under the definition of beautiful or fit in today's societies. Therefore, we see that this perception is higher in people who eat regularly and exhibit eating habits aimed at having a positive effect on their physical appearance (Verzija et al., 2018). Among the positive effects of psychology on nutrition is healthy eating. In addition, when individuals consume foods that they personally like and find delicious, it is observed that happiness hormones increase, and stress levels decrease. Today, it is known that caffeine lies under the coffee habit of many people. Since media, which can be described as mass control organs, play an effective role in the formation of human psychology and in the acquisition of self, identity and cultural habits of growing generations, the effect of such psychological influencing factors on nutritional habits has been proven by a study and at the same time some studies that need to be done in order to positively affect the psychology of children in the upbringing process. (Roberto, 2020).

Especially in developed societies, it is observed that turning to coffee to cope with stress and positively affecting the psychology of the person due to the active ingredients in coffee (Sanchez et al., 2022). The cognitive feelings of the individual can affect the physical appearances in the right proportion. For this reason, it is seen that there are people who change their diet, and it is known that the main reason is due to the increase in their self-esteem and the fact that they feel better psychologically due to the better physical appearance (Karsli, 2014). Another of the positive effects of psychology on nutrition is that the foods we consume when dealing with psychosocial problems calm us down and allow us to make more accurate decisions. When we consume foods that relax us psychologically (caffeine, carbohydrate, sugar, or water, etc.), it has been shown to relax physiologically while at the same time having a calming effect psychologically and helping us cope with situations such as anxiety (Arieputri et al., 2018). People who think that they will be depressed when they have obesity or excess weight regulate their eating habits and thus consume healthier foods due to this psychological effect. In addition, the psychological feeling that human beings need to pay attention to the

nutrients they receive due to the fear of death, which is one of the most basic instincts, can be given as an example of the positive effects of psychology on nutrition (Woods, 1981). Media content that encourages healthy eating affects people psychologically and due to the psychological stress pressure arising from this, individuals tend to consume healthier foods but at the same time try to gain regular eating habits (Roberto, 2020). Some people also say that coffee is an effective food in reducing the stress they experience psychologically and at the same time keeps them fitter before starting work (Streufert et al., 1997).

We can understand the relationship between psychology and nutrition in situations such as fear of weight gain, calorie calculation, eating something constantly even though you are not hungry or being able to eat only when you are alone (Şengönül, 2019). It is observed that individuals with high psychological self-esteem perform the feeding action more easily even in crowded environments. As a result of the positive psychology, individuals can make more careful choices while eating and at the same time regulate their eating habits accordingly (Wiggins et al., 2001). It is observed that the digestive systems of people who feel psychologically happy work faster and provide easier food digestion. For this reason, it is understood that the digestive systems of psychologically positive individuals work healthier after their nutrition. While the act of feeding is conducted, people aim to suppress the feeling of hunger while at the same time enjoying eating the food they like, so it is seen that people are psychologically relaxed and their stress levels decrease when they eat the foods they like psychologically (Sanchez et al., 2022). Eating habits differ between individuals. An athlete's eating habits are related to the profession in which they practice, but there is no regulating psychological factor that regulates the eating habits of a normal person. For this reason, psychologically, we need to address the factors that positively or negatively affect our eating habits. Consuming a psychologically loved food reduces our stress levels, while consuming a food we do not like will be the opposite. For this reason, individuals can choose their eating habits from among the foods they psychologically like, find useful or consider healthy (Takeda et al., 2004). In this way, it can be understood that psychologically occurring factors directly affect our eating habits. The eating habit that a person who is afraid of heart disease changes because of the fear impulse he experiences psychologically can be given as an example of the positive factors that psychology creates on nutrition. Many people have a common knowledge that vitamin D influences

reducing depression, but one study evaluated the relationship between vitamin D and depression and found no evidence (Gowda et al., 2015).

4. Examples of Psychological Impact Affecting Nutrition

Another of the positive effects of psychology on eating habits is the eating habits that the individual will do to increase self-esteem through his / her own physical appearance (Arganini et al., 2012). It is known that drinking enough water and eating healthy is important for skin health. Therefore, a person who wants to feel good psychologically will be affected by a positive effect by directing his eating habits to foods that regulate his health (Heuvel et al., 2019). Psychologically, people tend to buy products at eye level when they are hungry, so huge food companies pay high fees every year to place products on shelves at eye level and use those spaces (Roberto, 2020). Individuals are highly influenced by the foods they see and the desire to consume these products arises, so cartoons published in countries such as Australia do not allow cartoons that encourage children's unhealthy foods, and it is also known that cartoons promoting healthy foods are supported (Roberto, 2020). As it can be understood from here, it is observed that encouraging psychologically healthy foods is among the examples that can be given to create a factor that provides a positive effect on eating habits. Nowadays it is observed that when it is watered down to someone who is crying psychologically, it is easier to calm down, so it is understood that there is a direct connection between food and psychology. People who have experienced psychological sadness, trauma, or stress often say they feel low blood sugar and therefore have a desire to eat sweet things, but although this has not been proven, it is said that some foods trigger what we call emotional nutrition and cause us to consume more nutrients due to stress (Stephen, 1986). Our eating habits are influenced by factors such as physical condition, health, happiness, and hunger that we want psychologically. For this reason, people always tend to consume foods that they think are good for them in their work (Wood and Runger, 2016). Individuals who try to overcome their stress and emotional disorders with changes in their eating habits often tend to consume food, and research shows that when they exhibit these behaviors, they have a psychological alleviating effect on the trauma or situation they experience (Verzija et al., 2018). Another of the positive effects of psychology on nutrition is the body's need for healthy foods and the ease of digestion, the individual can say that he feels better psychologically when he consumes a healthy food and

at the same time it is observed that he can make healthier decisions (Schofield and Mullainathan, 2008). When the psychological pressure created by the concept of self-esteem is examined, it is observed that individuals make changes in their eating habits and diet to increase their self-esteem and feel better and make efforts to reach the body mass index predicted by society (Takeda et al., 2004). In psychological situations such as sudden sadness, loss of a job, loss of a close person or economic inadequacies, it has been observed that individuals change their eating habits although they differ and therefore the relationship between psychology and nutrition has once again been proven factually (Takeda et al., 2004).

5. Negative Effects of Psychology on Nutrition

Individuals who are depressed or diagnosed with anxiety tend to eat more than other people we consider normal (Macht and Simons, 2011). As can be understood, our psychological state has negative effects on our eating habits and these effects can later turn into physical disorders such as obesity. At the same time, it has been proven that psychologically stressed individuals are more inclined to harmful habits (Akfert et al., 2009). Self-esteem is among the most crucial factors affecting the importance we give to our physical appearance today. For this reason, individuals are psychologically exposed to stress and anxiety due to being overweight or underweight in their environment (Takeda et al., 2004). Psychologically, individuals with depression or anxiety often eat too much or rarely eat (Macht and Simons, 2011). As it can be understood from here, the nutritional habits of individuals may change due to psychological traumas or situations, and there are many negative effects on their health and eating habits. When the working and economic conditions in developed and developing countries are examined, it is seen that many individuals show the action we define as emotional eating or make changes in their eating habits to get rid of psychological stress (Lobera and Martínez, 2020). It is often observed that individuals with depression often perform the concept of emotional eating, and therefore rapid weight gains are observed (Nicholls et al., 2016). From a psychological point of view, it is seen that people with discomfort, stress or anxiety are more likely to suffer from obesity and this is a result of changing eating habits under the influence of psychological factors (Nicholls et al., 2016). It has been proven that harmful foods consumed in the daily feeding cycle can later cause many psychological disorders, including depression (Alpert and Fava, 1997).

Since the content in publications such as cartoons or advertisements in the media is psychologically effective in people and especially in children, it imparts harmful food habits and at the same time encourages individuals to unhealthy habits, restrictions and rules have been imposed on these publications in many countries (Roberto, 2020). It has been determined that psychologically affected individuals adopt harmful habits and have appetite in publications, and therefore it can be understood that the content in the media adversely affects our eating habits through our psychology and harms our health. Another negative effect of psychology on nutrition is the orientation of individuals to harmful foods in the face of psychological situations. Especially due to the working conditions and psychological stress in today's economic system, individuals tend to consume more carbohydrates, ready-made food, and harmful habits, and therefore gain unhealthy food habits due to psychological factors (Şengönül et al., 2019). When stress is considered as a psychological factor, situations such as emotional nutrition caused by stress are seen to be a noticeable change in the individual's eating habits and to consume more nutrients than normal (Arganini et al., 2012). Individuals' eating habits may vary according to the situations such as happiness, stress, and sadness they participate in, and the results of these behaviors can lead to many serious health problems, including obesity (Şengönül et al., 2019). Self-esteem and the beauty perception of individuals are analyzed in direct connection with external appearance and weight today, and therefore a great psychological perception formation is seen in society. For such reasons, individuals experience stress due to the psychological pressure they are exposed to in their eating habits and at the same time they consume food outside of what they want to keep up with society by changing their eating patterns (Şengönül et al., 2019). Psychologically depressed individuals can also suffer from obesity more easily because individuals who encounter stress or psychological trauma make changes in their eating habits and tend to frequent food consumption and unbalanced nutrition, and therefore it can be clearly understood that there is a two-sided relationship between obesity and psychology (Rooke and Thorsteinsson, 2008). Self-esteem, obesity, and depression are related to each other, and a study shows that the factors that affect the nutrition of people who are depressed are related to psychology and nutrition due to nutritional habits or economic deficiencies that usually result in obesity (Hamurcu, 2014). The most important of the negative effects of psychology on nutrition is the orientation of individuals to alcohol and its derivative harmful foods while under stress. Today, it is seen that in situations of stress or anxiety due to work, economy or different psychological factors,

individuals change their eating habits and aim to relax psychologically by turning to foods harmful to the body such as alcohol (Langenbacher and Nathan, 1983).

In many of the psychological states experienced due to stress, changes in eating habits such as excessive food consumption, orientation to alcohol or lack of appetite are frequently encountered (Eşel, 2005). Among the most common physical ailments in the world is Obesity and is often linked to psychology. Psychological factors play an especially key role in the formation of obesity and are emerging as triggering factors today (Trasande, 2010). Stress is among the most common causes that psychologically affect and negatively affect our eating habits, and the consumption of wrong food habits due to stress is the most important of the negative effects of psychology on eating habits (Trasande, 2010). The fact that the treatment of factors that adversely affect our eating habits psychologically is not common and that individuals engage in excessive or low food consumption behavior to eliminate their stress or psychological breakdowns is also one of the negative effects of psychology on eating habits (Macht and Simons, 2011).

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

It is observed that psychological factors cause many positive and negative effects on our eating habits (Gibson, 2006). For this reason, many factors such as media, work, culture, and gender play a key role in the formation of psychological stress and the shaping of our eating habits. In case of stress-induced disorders such as emotional nutrition, it is possible to experience health problems up to obesity (Lobera and Martínez, 2020). However, psychological pressures such as fear of death and healthy eating also have positive effects on our eating habits. Healthy diets that athletes follow to be more successful are one of the positive effects of psychological stress (Woodman and Hardy, 2001). Since psychological pressures trigger the concept of self-esteem, many people apply difficult diets and eating habits because they think that they can make their beauty perception and appearance better today, and these actions are effective in having a negative effect on their psychology eating habits. Today, when individuals encounter situations such as depression, trauma, or anxiety psychologically, they change their eating habits due to psychological effects. As a result of these changes, many negative situations such as obesity, health problems and heart diseases may occur because of situations such as too much food consumption and turning to harmful foods (Macht and Simons, 2011). It is seen that individuals consume more food due to stress and disorders up to obesity are caused by changes in

nutritional habits caused by psychological stress (Güven, 2014). Especially thanks to certain limitations that can be made in the media and the encouragement to useful foods, it can be ensured that individuals are encouraged to eat healthier foods from an early age and in this way, this teaching can be added to the individual identities of the same individuals to be more careful when raising future generations. As well as individuals who are psychologically depressed, at the same time, individuals who are negatively affected psychologically due to their eating habits are included in the society (Lobera and Martínez, 2020). Today, due to the perceptions of beauty loaded on gender and gender, many people experience psychological stress and anxiety, so they adjust their eating habits accordingly and may even face negative eating habits such as malnutrition. Psychologically, programs aimed at building self-esteem can allow individuals to regulate their eating habits and at the same time exhibit more positive attitudes towards the anxiety or stress situations they experience psychologically. It has been observed that people with obesity may become psychologically depressed more quickly than other people and at the same time tend to consume more food due to stress (Şengönül et al., 2019). Psychologically directing individuals to healthier food consumption through studies aimed at regulating eating habits can play a key role in regulating both current and future eating habits of society and individuals (Kavas and Kavas, 1985). In psychological situations such as depression and stress, individuals getting professional help and dietitians cooperating with psychologists to prepare an appropriate nutrition plan for individuals who are psychologically exposed to these factors can help reduce or eliminate the negative effects of psychology on eating habits (Berberoğlu and Hocaoğlu, 2021). It is seen that the foods that individuals eat during infancy and childhood have a prominent place in their psychology when they become adults, and at the same time, individuals consume almost no food that they overeat as children when they become adults. While our psychology plays such an important role on our eating habits, in order for us to gain a healthy, regular and quality eating habit, it will be beneficial for individuals with regular and healthy eating habits to work on nutrition programs or the promotion of healthy foods in the presence of both dietitians and psychologists from a young age (Sanchez et al., 2022).

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